

A quantitative study of this hydrolytic decomposition has also been made and this forms the subject matter of the present paper. The results obtained definitely support the above representation and confirm the constitution previously suggested for the two varieties of the acid.

The decomposition of the *iso*-acid was quantitatively studied by distilling the solid acid with dilute HCl. The liberated H₂S gas was absorbed in an ammoniacal cadmium salt solution. The precipitated CdS was dissolved in an excess of standard iodine solution, and the amount of sulphidic sulphur (H₂S) was estimated as usual.

A yellowish brown slimy residue was left behind in the distilling flask. This was filtered and the amount of sulphuric acid (SO₃) in the filtrate was estimated as BaSO₄.

The yellowish brown slimy residue, on treatment with NaOH solution, gave a bluish green residue of Co (OH)₂ and a filtrate containing [Co (CN)₆]^{'''} ion. The slimy residue also contained free S as was proved by digestion with KCN solution and then testing for KSCN with FeCl₃. This proves that the slimy, yellowish brown residue is a cobaltous cobalticyanide. The Cobaltous compounds evidently resulted from the decomposition of the aquo-pentacyano-cobaltic acid, one of the products of hydrolysis of the complex *iso*-thiosulphato-pentacyano-cobaltic acid.

The filtrate from the slimy precipitate contained a simple cobaltous salt as CoCl₂ or CoSO₄.

RESULTS.

I. A sample of the *iso*-acid containing 18.3% Co gave on distillation with HCl:

$$S'' \text{ (sulphidic)} = 4.14\% ; \quad S \text{ (as SO}_4''\text{)} = 9.2\%.$$

$$\therefore \text{Co} : S'' : S(\text{SO}_4'') = 1 : 0.42 : 0.935.$$

II. Another sample containing 17.56% Co gave on distillation with HCl:

$$S'' \text{ (as H}_2\text{S)} = 5.38\% ; \quad S \text{ (as SO}_4''\text{)} = 9.1\%.$$

$$\therefore \text{Co} : S'' : S(\text{SO}_4'') = 1 : 0.56 : 0.95.$$

III. A third sample containing 16.15% Co gave on distillation with acid:

$$S'' \text{ (as H}_2\text{S)} = 5.64\% ; \quad S \text{ (as SO}_4''\text{)} = 8.1\%.$$

$$\therefore \text{Co} : S'' : S(\text{SO}_4'') = 1 : 0.642 : 0.923,$$

The cobalt in the filtrate from the slimy precipitate was determined after precipitation of H_2SO_4 . It contained 9.8 Co, i.e., about 60.7% of the total Co present in the *iso*-acid.

Similar results were obtained by distillation with water alone for a somewhat longer time.

The variation in the percentage of total Co in the different samples of the *iso*-acid was due to the difference in the water of hydration of the acid, (cf. Rây and Maulik, *loc. cit.*).

DISCUSSION.

Considering the equation II for the hydrolysis of the *iso*-acid, it follows that the proportion of Co : S'' : S(SO₄'') should be 1 : 1 : 1. The estimated value for S as SO₄'' in all the samples examined is in fair agreement with this ratio, though the result is always lower (about 5.7%). This can be accounted for by the fact that the solid *iso*-acid undergoes a slight decomposition at the laboratory temperature (25-27°) with separation of S and SO₂ (*vide* equation II).

The amount of sulphidic sulphur has not been found to exceed 64% of the theoretical value. This has to be accounted for. The sulphur present in the slimy precipitate evidently makes up this deficit, and the appearance of about 60% of the total Co of the *iso*-acid as Co'' in the filtrate from the slimy residue, as well as the formation of cobaltous cobalticyanide, are in perfect agreement with this fact. This becomes clear when we consider the decomposition of aquo-pentacyano-cobaltic acid, one of the primary products of hydrolysis of the *iso*-acid. The aquo-pentacyano-cobaltic acid, being not a very stable compound, undergoes decomposition in the boiling solution.

In the boiling solution, cobaltic cyanide decomposes into cobaltous sulphate and oxygen, or into cobaltous chloride and chlorine in the presence of HCl. The oxygen or the chlorine liberated acts upon H_2S which is thus oxidised to S and H_2O . The sulphuric acid and hydrogen sulphide are produced by the hydrolysis of β -thiosulphuric acid.

The presence of Co⁺⁺ in the filtrate from the slimy precipitate and of S in the latter, as well as the defect of sulphur in the distillate, are thus clearly explained. The nature and composition of the slimy precipitate also agrees perfectly with this representation.

Bassett and Durrant (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 1416) have come to the conclusion that thiosulphuric acid decomposes according to the three reversible reactions:

Foerster (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, 177, 61) however, disagrees with the view that thiosulphuric acid leads to the formation of trithionic acid and H₂S by decomposition. Recently Prakke and Stiasny (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1933, 52, 615) have shown that the decomposition of thiosulphuric acid proceeds in two directions depending on the *p_H* value of the solution: (1) formation of S and H₂SO₃ and (2) formation of polythionates, mainly S₅O₆^{''} (pentathionate).

They too, therefore, disagree with Bassett and Durrant's view (*loc. cit.*). In no case they have found that ordinary thiosulphuric acid give more than traces of H₂S by decomposition in solution. The liberation of H₂S from thiosulphuric acid under any circumstance is attributed by them to the isomeric form of thiosulphuric acid.

As a result of experimental observations regarding the decomposition of the above described complex acid, it can be concluded that thiosulphuric acid is capable of existence in two different isomeric forms, α- and β-modifications. Of these the α-form decomposes as usual into H₂SO₃ and S, whereas the β-form gives rise to H₂S and H₂SO₄ on decomposition. Because, in the experiments described above, almost quantitative formation of H₂SO₄ cannot be accounted for according to Bassett and Durrant's second equation, unless it is assumed that the whole of the thiosulphuric acid decomposes in the sense of their second equation into H₂S and H₂S₃O₆, and the latter (H₂S₃O₆) is then quantitatively hydrolysed into H₂SO₄ and H₂S (*cf.* Bassett and Durrant, *loc. cit.*) as follows:

That trithionic acid will thus completely hydrolyse in boiling acid solution without giving SO_2 and S is rather unlikely, and direct evidence thereto is completely lacking.

Even assuming, after Bassett and Durrant, that thiosulphuric acid can decompose into H_2S and H_2SO_4 through the intermediate formation of $\text{H}_2\text{S}_3\text{O}_6$, a complete quantitative decomposition of this type will naturally justify the conclusion that thiosulphuric acid can exist in a second isomeric modification differing from the usual form, which decomposes more or less quantitatively into H_2SO_3 and S. The constitution of these two modifications has already been discussed in previous contributions (Rây, *loc. cit.*).

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